

Understanding the Role of Sirtuins in the Pathogenesis and Treatment of Oral Ulcers: A Rapid Review

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Abstract:

Oral ulcers are a prevalent clinical condition with multifactorial etiologies, including trauma, infections, systemic diseases, and immune dysregulation. Sirtuins, particularly SIRT1, play an important role in regulating oxidative stress, inflammation, and cellular repair pathways. This rapid review, conducted using the PRISMA protocol, synthesizes current evidence on the role of sirtuins in oral ulcer pathophysiology and their potential as therapeutic targets. A comprehensive search identified 140 articles in PubMed, 41 in ScienceDirect, and 4 in the Cochrane Library, of which 1 study met the eligibility criteria. The findings indicate that

SIRT1 expression in the oral ulcer rats model is significantly lower than in normal controls, whereas NF- κ B and TNF- α levels are markedly elevated in the control group. Pharmacological activation of SIRT1 attenuates inflammation, highlighting its therapeutic potential. However, the limited sample sizes and the lack of clinical trials specifically addressing oral ulcers restrict the generalizability of these findings. Additional study is needed to validate these findings and investigate SIRT1-targeted treatments.

Keywords: *Sirtuin, Sirt1, oral ulcer, recurrent aphthous stomatitis.*

Introduction

Oral ulcers are defined as localized disruptions of the oral mucosa's integrity, often extending to the surrounding connective tissue, producing a distinct crateriform look. The associated

symptoms, particularly pain, significantly impair quality of life, impacting essential activities such as eating and speaking (Lewis, & Lamey, 2023; Zeng, et al., 2022). The etiology of oral ulcers is multifactorial, encompassing local factor including trauma (mechanical, physical, and

chemical), infectious, allergic, as well as systemic factors like skin to the surrounding connective tissue, producing a distinct crateriform look. disorders, autoimmune diseases, tumors, and inflammatory bowel disease (Rawlings, & Willis, 2023). Most oral ulcers arise from a combination of local and systemic factors. The molecular mechanisms underlying oral ulcers remain incompletely understood, which emphasize the need for effective treatment approaches to treat chronic or recurrent cases (Qin, et al., 2018; Lau, & Smith, 2022).

The sirtuin (SIRT), class III histone deacetylases protein, has garnered attention for its regulatory roles in cellular homeostasis. In mammals, seven sirtuin members (SIRT1–7) have been identified (Chen, et al., 2023). Emerging evidence indicates that sirtuin have essential parts in regulation of oxidative stress, inflammation, and tissue repair, making them promising therapeutic targets for oral ulcers (Sun, et al., 2024; You, & Liang, 2023; Wu, et al., 2022). This review aims to synthesize recent evidence on the role of sirtuins in oral ulcer pathophysiology, emphasizing their therapeutic potential and emerging applications.

Materials and Methods

Search Strategy and Study Selection

This review followed the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) protocol (Page, et al., 2021). A systematic literature search was conducted in PubMed, ScienceDirect, and cochrane databases for articles published between January 2015 and January 2025. The search was conducted using Boolean operators "AND" and "OR" with terms included "sirtuin", "SIRT*", "oral ulcer", "oral ulceration", "aphthous stomatitis", "recurrent aphthous stomatitis", and "traumatic ulcer".

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The Inclusion criteria were studies investigating the role of sirtuins in oral ulcers, aphthous stomatitis, or oral mucositis. With study design randomized control trials, human studies, and/or animal studies. Article available in English and available in full texts. The exclusion criteria were non-peer-reviewed articles, reviews

article, and studies focusing exclusively on non-oral tissues.

Two investigators worked on the process of synthesize literature. They extracted data then compared their findings. The third investigator was involved for consultation If disagreed emerged. This investigator decided on a resolution.

Results

Study Selection

In all, 140 articles were identified through searches in the PubMed database, 41 article in ScienceDirect and 4 articles in the Cochrane Library database. We included 1 article for the review after screening for eligibility criteria. The process of systematic search according to PRISMA guidelines is briefly shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of Article Search Based on the PRISMA Method

Summary of The Result

One animal study describes the differences between Sirt1 level in oral mucosa of normal

model and oral ulcer rats model (Table 1). Treatment with Zhibaidihuang decoction

(ZBDHD) modulate Sirt1 expression and suppress the expression of NF- κ B and TNF α .

Table 1. Article Synthesis Result

Sirtuin	Role	Treatment	Method	Mechanism	References
Sirt1	Reccurent oral ulcer (ROU)	Zhibaidihuang decoction (ZBDHD)	immunohistochemistry (IHC)	The Sirt1 expression in oral mucosa of ROU model rats was lower than normal group. Conversely, t NF- κ B and TNF- α level were higher in control group. Treatment with Zhibaidihuang decoction (ZBDHD) modulate Sirt1 expression and downregulates NF- κ B and TNF α expression	¹¹

Discussion

Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) was first identified as a crucial coenzyme for energy metabolism. Sirtuin, a family of NAD⁺-dependent enzymes, is essential for preserving cellular homeostasis because it stimulates the post-translational modification (PTM) of several enzymes and signaling pathways (You, & Liang, 2023; Singh, et al., 2018). SIRT1, SIRT6, and SIRT7 are the three of the seven mammalian sirtuins that are predominantly nuclear, SIRT2 resides in the cytoplasm, while SIRT3, SIRT4, and SIRT5 are localized in mitochondria, where they regulate energy metabolism (Chen, et al., 2023).

SIRT1 influences cellular metabolism, stress resistance, DNA repair, and inflammation, making it a promising target for managing oral ulcerative conditions (Chen, et al., 2023). SIRT1 exhibits anti-inflammatory activity by downregulating nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) as important inflammatory pathways. It is suppressing NF- κ B activity and the expression of downstream inflammatory cytokines by deacetylates the NF- κ B p65 subunit (Yang, et al., 2012).

Evidence from this review demonstrates reduced SIRT1 expression and elevated NF- κ B and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) expression levels in the recurrent oral ulcer (ROU) model

rats compared to healthy controls. Interestingly, SIRT1 overexpression on Zhibaidihuang decoction (ZBDHD) group suppress NF- κ B and TNF α expression (Shao, et al., 2021). Similar findings were observed in studies using resveratrol, a SIRT1 activator, which reduced pro-inflammatory cytokine levels in a chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, further supporting SIRT1's pivotal role in inflammation regulation (Wang, et al., 2017).

NF- κ B as an essential inflammation regulator, promotes the synthesis of cytokines, adhesion molecules, inflammasome components, and chemokines (Liu, et al., 2017). NF κ B activation and its translocation into the nucleus induce a release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, which results in endothelial cells and fibroblasts damage (Al-Azri, et al., 2015). In oral ulcer, the inflammatory process and immune response significantly influence healing. A balanced expression of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines is essential for wound healing (Silva, et al., 2018). Excessive pro-inflammatory cytokine expression may delay wound healing, while anti-inflammatory cytokines limit pro-inflammatory signaling and suppress excessive immune responses, mitigating the negative effects of inflammation (Al-Qahtani, Alhamlan, & Al-Qahtani, 2024; Opal, & DePalo, 2000). Anti-inflammatory modulation has been shown to accelerate oral

ulcer healing by reducing pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-1 α , IL-1 β , and TNF- α (Silva, et al., 2018; Pan, et al., 2024).

Preclinical studies indicate that pharmacological upregulation of SIRT1 activity attenuates inflammation, demonstrating SIRT1's potential as targets for therapy for oral ulcer management. Future research should focus on assessing sirtuin activators' safety and effectiveness in treating mouth ulcers.

Limitations

This review identified only one preclinical study investigating the therapeutic potential of sirtuins in oral ulcers. Additional limitations include the lack of clinical trials and the small sample sizes of the included research, specifically addressing oral ulcer management. Furthermore, the heterogeneity in experimental models reduces the generalizability and applicability of the findings to broader contexts.

Conclusion

In the oral mucosa of recurrent oral ulcer (ROU) model rats, SIRT1 expression was significantly lower compared to the normal group. Conversely, NF- κ B and TNF- α levels were markedly elevated in the control group. Pharmacological upregulation of SIRT1 activity demonstrated an ability to attenuate inflammation, highlighting its therapeutic potential. However, the small sample sizes of the included research and the lack of clinical trials that explicitly target oral ulcers limit the available evidence. These limitations restrict the generalizability of the findings. Further research, including well-designed clinical trials, is essential to validate these results and explore the therapeutic implications of SIRT1 activation in oral ulcer management.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Al-Azri, A. R., Gibson, R. J., Bowen, J. M., Stringer, A. M., Keefe, D. M., & Logan, R. M. (2015). Involvement of matrix metalloproteinases (MMP-3 and MMP-9) in the pathogenesis of irinotecan-induced oral mucositis. *Journal of Oral Pathology & Medicine*, 44, 459–467. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jop.12255>
- Al-Qahtani, A. A., Alhamlan, F. S., & Al-Qahtani, A. A. (2024). Pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory interleukins in infectious diseases: A comprehensive review. *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/tropicalmed9010013>
- Chen, J., Wang, Q., Li, R., et al. (2023). The role of sirtuins in the regulation of oxidative stress during the progress and therapy of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Life Sciences*, 333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2023.122187>
- Lau, C. B., & Smith, G. P. (2022). Recurrent aphthous stomatitis: A comprehensive review and recommendations on therapeutic options. *Dermatology and Therapy*, 35. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.15500>
- Lewis, M. A. O., & Lamey, P. J. (2023). Oral ulceration (Part 1). *British Dental Journal*, 235, 869–874. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41415-023-6504-3>
- Liu, T., Zhang, L., Joo, D., & Sun, S. C. (2017). NF- κ B signaling in inflammation. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sigtrans.2017.23>
- Opal, S. M., & DePalo, V. A. (2000). Anti-inflammatory cytokines. *Chest*. <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.117.4.1162>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., et al. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *The BMJ*, 372. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
- Pan, Z., Zhang, X., Xie, W., et al. (2024). Revisited and innovative perspectives of oral ulcer: From biological specificity to local treatment. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2024.1335377>

- Qin, L., Kao, Y. W., Lin, Y. L., et al. (2018). Recurrent aphthous stomatitis may be a precursor or risk factor for specific cancers: A case-control frequency-matched study. *Cancer Medicine*, 7, 4104–4114. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cam4.1685>
- Rawlings, N., & Willis, A. (2023, April). Oral ulceration - Clinical feature. *Journal of the Irish Dental Association*. <https://doi.org/10.58541/001c.74191>
- Shao, Y., Ding, B., Ji, J., et al. (2021). The anti-inflammatory effect of Zhibaidihuang decoction on recurrent oral ulcer with Sirt1 as the key regulatory target. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2021, 8886699. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8886699>
- Silva, P. G. de B., de Codes, É. B. B., Freitas, M. O., Martins, J. O. de L., Alves, A. P. N. N., & Sousa, F. B. (2018). Experimental model of oral ulcer in mice: Comparing wound healing in three immunologically distinct animal lines. *Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology*, 22, 444. https://doi.org/10.4103/jomfp.JOMFP_144_17
- Singh, C. K., Chhabra, G., Ndiaye, M. A., Garcia-Peterson, L. M., MacK, N. J., & Ahmad, N. (2018). The role of sirtuins in antioxidant and redox signaling. *Antioxidants & Redox Signaling*, 28, 643–661. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2017.7290>
- Sun, H., Li, D., Wei, C., et al. (2024). The relationship between SIRT1 and inflammation: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 15, 1465849. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2024.1465849>
- Wang, X. L., Li, T., Li, J. H., Miao, S. Y., & Xiao, X. Z. (2017). The effects of resveratrol on inflammation and oxidative stress in a rat model of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Molecules*, 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22091529>
- Wu, Q. J., Zhang, T. N., Chen, H. H., et al. (2022). The sirtuin family in health and disease. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-022-01257-8>
- Yang, H., Zhang, W., Pan, H., et al. (2012). SIRT1 activators suppress inflammatory responses through promotion of p65 deacetylation and inhibition of NF- κ B activity. *PLoS One*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0046364>
- You, Y., & Liang, W. (2023). SIRT1 and SIRT6: The role in aging-related diseases. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Molecular Basis of Disease*, 1869. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbadis.2023.166815>
- Zeng, X., Jin, X., Zhong, L., et al. (2022). Difficult and complicated oral ulceration: An expert consensus guideline for diagnosis. *International Journal of Oral Science*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41368-022-00178-0>